
FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRACTICAL LEARNING PROCESSES BASED ON NEW PEDAGOGICAL AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: The article emphasizes the importance of properly selected pedagogical technologies in the educational process to improve the effectiveness of education.

Keywords: pedagogical technology, design, technology.

Education is the main factor in the reform of society and its transformation into a society more open to the outside world and focused on new technologies and knowledge [2, p. 177]. Special attention in the history of pedagogy and psychology has always been paid to the problem of activity, which is the basis of personality education since the first periods of its formation. Today's processes of globalization have changed the consciousness and consciousness of our youth. Students studying in higher education institutions do not differ much from adults in their worldview. Nevertheless, life itself dictates to them, as well as adults, continuous monitoring of their range of thinking in the audience.

Learning is an incredibly difficult process. Learning technology is an opportunity to achieve the learning goal using organizational and methodological tools. One of the features of student education at present is the improvement of the education system every day, as well as the personal qualities of the professional team, the requirements for knowledge, qualifications and skills that they should possess are increasing. After all, it cannot be said about today's specialist that he is not limited to the fact that a student studying in the classroom calmly masters the lectures of professors and teachers so that state educational standards enter into the

consciousness of a complex set of knowledge. Students should actively participate in the learning process so that they can consciously, thoroughly understand new information.

Modern education has extensive experience in maintaining the physical, mental, moral, spiritual and emotional development of a person. In the following years, textbooks were created at various stages of training, which were based on one or another advanced technology, both theoretically and methodologically. The novelty of these reference books lies in the fact that modern pedagogical technologies are described in detail as a real textbook for a teacher working with students studying at a university, taking into account various pedagogical conditions and opportunities. The ideas of beautiful, competent, responsive teachers quickly reach students and give them the opportunity to learn educational materials, and students look forward to such lessons. The system of requirements for the behavior of a teacher is of particular importance in the fulfillment by a teacher of his professional duties, moral obligations to society, the teaching staff and the student. The real pedagogical activity is to strengthen this method of dealing with students on the basis of an individual method. In our opinion, a teacher who works tirelessly independently and is interested in innovation can apply at least 10-12 different pedagogical technologies or methods simultaneously, that is, during one academic year. Whether he will use this method in a specific lecture or seminar session depends on his skill and logic of the same topic, on the pedagogical task assigned to him. The new manual can be said to reflect the pedagogical methods used by twelve teachers in covering twelve different topics. And so, if we take into account the abundance of professional teachers who are talented and have their own method of work, it is not difficult to imagine how multifaceted and diverse this process is, and such manuals can be overwhelming. The methodological basis of modern teaching aids.

In the context of globalization of education, there is a discrepancy between the field of education and the developing social needs of society. The education system faces the need to form a harmonious personality, reduce the imbalance between the educational sphere and the labor market, create a theory of modern pedagogical

technologies for the use of information technologies and achieve careful design of the educational process.

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